

Passive filler loaded polysilazane-derived glass/ceramic coating system on AISI 441 stainless steel: Corrosion behaviour

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ABSTRACT

This study describes a corrosion resistant environmental barrier coating (EBC) applied to an AISI 441 stainless steel substrate. For that purpose, four polymer derived ceramic (PDC) coating systems consisting of a bond coat applied by dip coating and a top coat loaded with a passive filler deposited by spray coating are developed. The selected samples of PDC layers (C2-GM, C4-PP) are studied from the point of view of their corrosion resistance in the flow-through atmosphere of synthetic air at the temperatures up to 1000 °C. The ceramic coatings for corrosion tests were pyrolysed in the air for 1 hour at the temperature of 800 °C. The compositions selected for detailed corrosion tests are summarized in Tab. 1

Tab. 1: Compositions of the composite top coats after pyrolysis (vol. %) and estimated thermal expansion coefficients; (GM = glass microspheres, PP = precursor powder)

Sample name	HTT 1800	YSZ	G8470	G018-311	G018-385	AYZ	CTE (10 ⁻⁶ /K)
C2-GM	20	37	17	17	-	9 (GM)	8.9
C4-PP	20	30	-	13	16	21 (PP)	8.5

Weight increment of uncoated and coated samples as a function of the time at various temperatures are shown in Fig. 1a-c. At all three temperatures, the weight increases rapidly in the early stages, up to 6 hours. At 900 °C the weight gain slows down after 6 h of corrosion and it is eventually stabilized at times exceeding 12 h, indicating that a diffusion barrier of corrosion products was formed at the steel's surface. At 950 °C and 1000 °C the initial fast corrosion slows down significantly after 6 h, but continuous, and approximately linear mass increase is observed. For coated samples (Fig. 1b, c) weight gains at temperatures 900 °C and 950 °C were negligible in the whole tested time interval. Small weight loss observed in the C2-GM coating after 1 h test at 950 °C which was attributed to error in weight determination.

Fig. 1: Mass gain of steel and coatings after oxidation tests a) steel b) coat C2-GM, c) coat C4-PP

Time dependence of phase composition of corroded samples obtained by Rietveld refinement of X-ray diffraction data of uncoated steel and C2-GM, C4-PP coated steel substrates at temperature 950 °C are shown in Fig. 2 a-c. From the XRD patterns of steel substrates (Fig. 2a) the phases Fe, Cr₂O₃, TiO₂ and spinel (Mn,Cr)₃O₄ were identified. In the case of coated samples (Fig. 2 b,c), the dominant phases at all tested temperatures in the initial stages of oxidation (up to 6h) are monoclinic and tetragonal ZrO₂. At longer exposure times and higher oxidation temperatures, crystallisation of the used glass fillers leads to the formation of new crystalline phases (Ba(AlSiO₄)₂ -hexacelsian, celsian), but also to the formation of new phases (YAG, YZr₈O₁₄) as a consequence of chemical reactions between the individual components of the layers. The product of substrate oxidation i.e. (Mn,Cr)₃O₄ was observed after 24 hours of exposure of coated samples at 1000 °C.

Fig. 2: Time dependence of phase composition of oxidized sample obtained by Rietveld refinement of X-ray diffraction data at the temperature 950 °C a) steel b) coat C2-GM, c) coat C4-PP

SEM micrographs of stainless steel and coatings after corrosion tests are shown in Fig. 3 a-c. The whole surface of uncoated steel is covered with a layer of oxide. In some cases, local delamination of the oxide layer (marked with the white arrows) was observed. After corrosion tests of coatings, there was a significant increase in the porosity of the layers and, accompanied by the growth of the pores and decrease of the coating thickness. Due to the softening of the used glass fillers, the cracks in the layers gradually healed, indicating at least partial protection of the metal substrate. A self-sealing process likely occurred during the test, allowing the protection of the stainless steel against further oxidation.

Fig. 3: Corrosion tests - microstructures a) steel 900°C/3h, b) C2-GM 950°C/6h, c) C4-PP 950°C/6h

Keywords: Corrosion, Passive filler, Polymer-derived ceramics

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